
IMPACT OF CONTINUOUS ASSESSMENT ON THE FINAL EXAMINATION SCORES OF STUDENTS IN MATHEMATICS IN OSUN STATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined how students' performance on term and promotion exams at secondary schools in Osun State Secondary was affected by continuous assessment. The researchers gathered information in a few of the state's local government secondary schools in Osun Central Senatorial District, six (6) public secondary schools and four (4) private schools were chosen at random for the study. The instruments that were used for the data collection are standardized questionnaire and the three most recent years of mathematics course results, also experimental group were exposed to these tests. Capacity workshop was organized for the experimental group. And the same term examination questions were used to examine both the experimental and the control groups. Data analyses were done using demographic data, correlation, regression and t-Test using the latest SPSS. The results showed that is a significant relationship between continuous assessment and final examination scores of students in mathematics based on the school ownership. It was recommended that high attention should be given to continuous assessments irrespective of students' gender and school ownership. Training and retraining of teachers should be prioritized in Nigerian secondary schools on the importance of continuous assessment in assessing students' academic strengths and performance.

Keywords: *Mathematics, Continuous Assessment, Examination Scores, Experimental Group, Students*

Introduction

In education, "assessment" refers to the broad range of techniques or instruments that teachers employ to assess, gauge, and record pupils' academic preparedness, learning progress, skill development, or educational requirements. This is due to the fact that education is a vital and necessary instrument for the industrialization and growth of any country, as demonstrated by the evaluation of students' performance in the classroom and beyond (Ukuije, 2001). Assessment can also be said to be any procedure or activity that is designed to collect information about the knowledge, attitude, or skills of the learner or group of learners. In the view of Omoifo (2006), what is termed "assessment in many schools today is summative, final, administrative, rigorous and content-driven rather than formative, diagnostic, private, suggestive and goal oriented, as such can be regarded as grading." Summative assessment entails the focus on final examinations by teachers, parents and students. Surprisingly, formative assessment is geared towards the consolidation of students' performance in the final examinations rather than inculcating students with problem solving, critical thinking, and life skills. Continuous Assessment (CA) is the term for assessment that is conducted as an ongoing procedure. According to Ogunnyi (2004), continuous assessment is a formative evaluation process that aims to systematically determine the total gains a student has made in knowledge, attitudes, and abilities following a particular set of learning experiences. It is more than just administering exams; continuous assessment encompasses all of the decisions a teacher makes in the classroom to raise students' academic performance. It is not just continuous testing.

One of the scientific disciplines that has made a huge global contribution to scientific and technological growth is mathematics. Many believed that success in modern society required a strong foundation in mathematics.

Its importance was demonstrated by its contributions to the sciences, technology, commerce for economic expansion, and the improvement of educational systems worldwide (Tella, 2008; Ampofo, 2019). Additionally, according to Ebisine (2013), mathematics is the study of symbolic language, numbers and numeration systems, sizes, patterns, shapes, and spaces. It can help in a big way to generalize and demonstrate relationships between variables.

Scholars and authors in the fields of sociology, psychology, educational sciences, and related subfields have explored the factors influencing students' academic success in literature, and they have proposed a number of ideas regarding these elements. While some academics placed greater emphasis on an individual's internal traits (such as intelligence, self-concept, etc.), others thought that an individual's external traits—such as social standing, family, and educational setting—were equally significant. Nonetheless, education is one of the key pillars of development (Garkaza, Banimahd, & Esmailic, 2011). The foundation of this research was system theory. A system is made up of several connected pieces that work together to form a whole. Aristotle proposed that the whole is more than the sum of its parts around 384 BC, which is whence system theory originated (Nwankwo, 1982). According to Christensen & Basilgan (2013), quoting Koontz, O'Donnell, & Weihrich (1980), the system is "a set of things connected or interdependent to form a complex unity; a whole composed of parts on orderly arrangement according to some scheme of plan." It is also the assembly of individuals, materials, ideas, and practices meant to carry out certain tasks or advance an objective (Christensen & Basilgan, 2013). From the aforementioned, it can be seen that every part of human life is a system, including the body, the educational system, governmental organizations, and enterprises, each of which has its own subsystems.

Because of the applicability of the educational system and the principles of interaction and interdependence of components with the wider system, the system theory is pertinent to educational management. This justification explains how the transformational process converts educational inputs into outputs, and so makes this study pertinent to system theory in education. The term “assessment” is commonly used during the evaluation of students, both at the commencement stage and at the completion of the course. The outcome of the assessment is useful in making a decision and in providing information on the extent to which the students have benefitted in a particular course or subject. The evaluators based their conclusions on the length of time spent assessing the pupils' worth and aptitude. To assess the degree to which students have profited from a course of study, educators want this kind of data (Onihunwa, Adigun, Irunokhai, Sada, Jeje, Adeyemi & Adesina, 2018). Turnbull and Hornby (2013) define assessment as the process of evaluating or appraising something. According to Atondo, Abah, and Naakaa (2019), it can also be understood as the act of passing judgment on something.

The process of gathering information for the purpose of making a decision—in this example, on the academic performance of students is known as assessment. According to Iljazi (2013), student assessment is just as significant as the actual teaching process. Students gain clarity about what matters, what counts, how they will use their time, and how they see themselves as learners through assessment. Modify the evaluation procedures if you wish to alter the way that students learn (Azzah, 2015). Studies on the relationship between academic achievement and continuous assessment showed that many students passed the CA but struggled in the course and final test. There was no significant relationship observed between the final exam scores and the CA scores. As a result, the pass/fail percentages for the CA differ from those for the midterm and final exams (Azzah, 2015). Furthermore, students' performance on their final semester exam in postsecondary institutions is well predicted by their CA scores (Onihunwa, et al., 2018). Similarly, studies on the relationship between gender and academic achievement showed no discernible difference in the practical physics performance of men and women.

This suggests that there is no way in which the performance of one gender can influence the performance of the other. It implies that because they are independent of one another, it is impossible to anticipate how well male or female students would achieve (Aina, 2013). Additionally, Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) found a marginal gender effect on the achievement of male and female students in relation to the mean scores of social studies students. For both boys and girls, Kashu (2014) found that overall performance was fair across all topics over the five years under investigation (2007–2011), with boys performing better in science courses than girls, who excelled in Home. The study's further findings indicated that while male students outperformed female pupils in terms of performance, the difference was not statistically significant. Gender has no bearing on students' chemistry performance in NECO, according to Adesoji and Kenni's (2013) theory, but it has a major impact on WASSCE chemistry students' academic achievement. The study conducted by Eze, Ezenwafor, and Obi (2015) demonstrated a noteworthy distinction in academic achievement between pupils based on their age and gender.

Data Analysis Techniques

The result of findings and discussion are presented based on respondents' demographic information of the research questions, and hypotheses. The Likert scale: strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD) for the questionnaire. Descriptive Statistics of percentage and mean with inferential statistics of t-

test and correlation method were employed to answer and test the study's research questions and hypotheses respectively. Frequency counts and mean scores were used for the research questions while *t*-test and regression analysis were applied to measure the significance of difference and correlation among the moderating variables used for the research. Level of significance was fixed at 95% and $p < 0.05$ was considered to be significant.

Results

Quantitative research method was used by administering questionnaires to gathered data. This research will be conducted in Osun Central Senatorial District in Nigeria. One hundred (100) Senior Secondary Schools Mathematics teachers were randomly selected across the Senatorial district and were given the prepared questionnaires out of which ninety (90) were recovered for analysis. Consent was sought from the participants through the form of a letter to the school authorities before we administered questionnaires. The participants were assured of confidentiality of their personal data. All collected data were subsequently treated with utmost confidentiality.

Table 1: Respondents' Demographic information

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Male</i>	52	57.8
<i>Female</i>	38	42.2
Total	90	100.0

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>1-26 years</i>	35	38.9
<i>27-35 years</i>	40	44.4
<i>36- 49 years</i>	10	11.1
<i>50years and above</i>	5	5.6
Total	90	100.0

The above table illustrates that a wide and rather balanced variety of participants were consulted. This implies that the researchers sought data from a wide spectrum of participants in order to give credence to the quality of data gathered. Most of the respondents possess diverse features. As shown in the table, 52 (57.8%) respondents are male, and female are 38 (42.2%). 35 (38.9%) respondents are less than 27 years old, 40 (44.4%) are in the age range of 27- 35 years, 10 (11.1%) are between 36-49 years, while only 5 (5.6%) respondents are 50 years old and above.

Table 2 (Professional Association)

Professional Association	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN)</i>	16	17.8
<i>Mathematics Teachers Association of Nigeria (MTAN)</i>	4	4.4
<i>Nigeria Union of Teachers (NUT)</i>	52	57.8
<i>Not Indicated</i>	18	20.0
Total	90	100.0

Teaching experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>5-10 years</i>	50	55.6
<i>11-20 years</i>	22	24.4
<i>21 years and above</i>	18	20.0
Total	90	100.0

Highest Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>PhD</i>	7	7.8
<i>MPhil or MSc/MTech</i>	28	31.1
<i>BSc./HND</i>	52	57.8
<i>ND/NCE</i>	3	3.3
Total	90	100.0

Table 2 above indicates that, 16 (17.8%) of the teachers registered with the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN); 4 (4.4%) are members of the Mathematics Teachers Association; 54 (57.8%) are members of the Nigeria Union of Teachers. While 18 (20.0%) did not indicate their professional association. In addition, 50 (55.6%) respondents have 5-10 years' experience, 22 (24.4%) have 11-20 years of experience, while 18 (20.0%) respondents have 21 years and above. Then, 7 (7.8%) had Ph.D, 28 (31.1%) are masters' graduates, 52 (57.8) had BSc/HND certificates and only 3 (3.3%) of the teachers are ND/NCE holders

Table 3: Summary of results on the conduct of CA in Mathematics in Schools.

Times/term	Frequency	Percent (%)
<i>Never</i>	0	0
<i>Once</i>	5	5.6
<i>Twice</i>	11	12.2
<i>More than twice</i>	74	82.0
Total	90	100.0

As indicated in Table 3, 74 (82.2%) respondents conduct continuous assessment more than two (2) times during a term in teaching Mathematics, twice 11 (12.2%) use to conduct only 2 times in a term during the teaching and learning process in the teaching of mathematics, only 5 (5.6%) teachers use to conduct continuous assessment once during the teaching and learning period in a term, while no teacher (0%) is in the habit of not conducting continuous assessment within a term. This means that most of the respondents actually know the value of continuous assessment in the teaching and learning of mathematics as a subject in secondary schools. From the findings above, it implies that most Mathematics teachers in Osun State combine both the continuous assessment and the final examination grades into consideration. As this is in line with Patel's (2013) who observed that given continuous assessment to student many times as possible help the students to always know their weaknesses and strength before the real examination.

Research Question 1: *Do students' scores in continuous assessment have any correlation with their final examination grade scores in mathematics?*

Table 4: Summary of results showing correlation scores between C.A and Final Examination.

Grade in Mathematics						
Question	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
<i>Preparation of C.A in Mathematics helps tremendously in the final examination</i>	11	21	27	31	2.16	0.97
	12.2%	23.3%	30.0	34.4%		
<i>Continuous Assessment in Mathematics enhance scoring very high marks in my final examination</i>	17	25	34	14	2.63	0.91
	18.9%	27.8%	37.8%	15.5%		
<i>Evaluation of Mathematics via C.A helps in no small measure than final examination</i>	21	51	15	3	3.23	0.69
	23.3%	56.7%	16.7%	3.3%		
<i>Positive association always exists between C.A and final exam grade scores</i>	31	37	16	6	3.11	0.87
	34.4%	41.1%	17.8%	6.7%		
<i>My colleagues help in no small measure in preparation for mathematics examination than continuous assessments</i>	12	22	40	16	2.42	0.95
	13.3	24.4%	44.5%	17.8%		
<i>I often prepare better for mathematics examinations than for tests and assignments</i>	27	39	20	4	3.07	0.78
	30.0%	43.3%	22.2%	4.5%		
<i>I prefer more often continuous assessment to final examinations</i>	58	23	5	4	3.56	0.67
	64.4%	25.6%	5.6%	4.4%		
<i>I prefer more often continuous assessment to final examinations</i>	29	34	19	8	2.89	0.87
	32.2%	37.8%	21.1%	8.9%		

Weighted Mean = 2.89
 Criterion = 2.50

It can be seen from Table 4 above, 11 (12.2%) respondents strongly agree that preparation for C.A in Mathematics helps tremendously in the final examination 21 (23.3%) agree, 27 (30.0%) disagree and 31 (34.4%) strongly disagree. Also, 17 (18.9) respondents strongly agree that C.A in Mathematics enhance scoring very high marks in my final examination, 25 (27.5%) agree, 34 (37.8%) disagree, while 14 (15.5%) strongly disagree. Furthermore, 21 (23.3%) respondents strongly agree that evaluation of Mathematics via C.A helps in no small measure than final examination, 51 (56.7%) agree, 15 (16.7%) disagree, while 3 (3.3%) strongly disagrees. 31 (34.4%) respondents strongly agree that positive association always exists between continuous assessment and final exam grade score, 37 (41.4%) agree, 16 (17.8%) disagree, while only 6 (6.7%) strongly disagree. 12 (13.3%) respondents strongly agree that colleagues help in no small measure in preparation for mathematics examination than continuous assessments, 22 (24.4%) agree, 40 (44.5%) disagree, while 16 (17.8) strongly disagree. Also, 27 (30.0%) respondents strongly agree that they often prepare better for mathematics examinations than the tests and assignments, 39 (43.3%) agree, 20 (22.2%) disagree, while only 4 (4.5%) strongly disagree. 58 (64.4%) respondents strongly agree that more errors are prone to be committed during the final examination due to limited time during the continuous assessment. 23 (25.6%) agree, 5 (5.6%) disagree, while 4 (4.4%) strongly disagree. Lastly, 29 (32.2%) strongly agree that they prefer more often continuous assessment to final examination, 34 (37.8%) agree, 19 (21.1%) disagree, while 8 (8.9%). This reveals that, serious collaboration is enhanced when practicing mathematics for final examination with peers and colleagues than continuous assessments. Thus the grand

mean score for students' perceived relationship between continuous assessments for students in mathematics found to be expedient for students' better performance in their final examinations, thereby having positive correlation with their final examination grade scores in mathematics considering the obtained weighted mean value of 2.89 is greater than the criterion of 2.50,

H₀: continuous assessment performance has significant impact on the final examination grade score in Mathematics

H₁: continuous assessment performance has no significant impact on the final examination grade score in Mathematics

Table 5: Table of regression on the influence of continuous assessment on final examination grade score in Mathematics

Variables	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig. (p value)	Remark
	B	Std Error	Beta(β)			
(Constant)	16.826	1.422		11.137	.000	
Continuous assessment	1.704	.307	.026	.306	.761	Not Sig.

Table 5 shows that the having good grades in continuous assessment determined the final examination grade score in Mathematics, the regression weight (β), the error of estimate ($SE\beta$), the coefficient, the t-ratio and the level at which the t-ratio is not significant. As indicated in the table, good C.A scores did not determines the final examination grade score ($\beta=0.026$, $t=0.306$, $p>0.05$) did not test significant on the teaching of Mathematics. This implies that having good grades in continuous assessment do not determined good grades in the final examination score. It does not have a significant influence on the final examination grade scores of Mathematics at secondary school level in Osun state. The null hypothesis was therefore accepted.

H₀: There is significant impact of continuous assessment on the final examination grade scores of students in mathematics in the public and private secondary schools.

H₁: There is no significant impact of continuous assessment on the final examination grade scores of students in mathematics in the public and private secondary schools.

Table 6: Regression on the impact of continuous assessment on the final examination grade scores of students in mathematics in the public and private secondary schools.

Variables	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig. (p value)	Remark
	B	Std Error	Beta (β)			
(Constant)	13.226	.514		19.685	.000	
Continuous Assessment	1.762	.277	.388	4.063	.000	Not Sig.

Looking at the regression analysis in table 6, continuous assessment and final examination grade score tested significant on the ownership of the secondary schools in Osun central senatorial district in Osun state, Nigeria, ($\beta=0.388$, $t=4.063$, $p<0.05$). The null hypothesis was therefore accepted since the p value is less than the table value we conclude that there is significant impact based on the ownership secondary schools in Osun State. By inference, there was a significant difference between performance of students in CA and final examination scores in mathematics based on schools' ownership.

Discussion of Results

This study is not actually intended to advise the uses of CA or determining its priority among the other methods of assessments. This is because the assessment method or tool is not the target but its impact on the students and the learning process is the goal. Students modify learning according to the method of assessment that used by the assessor. Through the CA system of assessment, the students are continuously under assessment and on an ongoing process of learning. Continuous assessment has influence on both students' Final Examination Result and on overall students' assessment. The implication is that students' academic achievement especially in mathematics was influenced by considerable level of knowledge and expertise employed for assessing students' performance on continuous assessments according to Van der Vleuten and Schuwirth (2005) that CA is an effective tool that is used to evaluate what it was intended or presupposed to measure. Trottera (2006) averred also that CA facilitates high level of inspirations to students to learn continuously on a daily basis. Thereby providing the needed response and feedback to students about their learning and alternative way of improving performances (Nitko, 2004). Continuous use of CA will tremendously assists teachers to identify each learner's areas of strength and weakness (Hernandez, 2012) and how such could be helped where necessary. Anaf and Yamin (2014) describe CA to include all strategies implemented by teachers to ascertain the knowledge, the understanding and the skills gained by students and frequent interactions between teachers and students. Proper utilization of CA enables teachers to have better comprehension of strength and weakness of the learners (Hernandez, 2012).

Study carried out by Carrillo and Pérez (2012) agreed with this study that CA shows higher level of correlation and this demonstrates considerable improvement in students' academic achievement. However, studies on the moderating influence on gender showed inconsistent results. The analysed data based on the gender difference disagreed with Bichi,

Suleiman and Ali (2019) that the female students had higher mean score than their male counterparts in academic achievement in mathematics.

Studies conducted by Emmanuel and Clement (2012) and Adeniyi, Ogli, Ojabo and Musa (2013) concurred with this study that CA had a good deal of influence on the FER of students. The demonstration of high correlation between CA and FER exemplified the relatedness of connectivity that frequent conduction of CA is pointer for students' improved performance in FER in mathematics.

Conclusion

As this study suggest the existence of relationship between continuous assessment and examination scores in mathematics in Osun central senatorial district secondary, the findings exemplified high correlation between Continuous Assessment and Final Examination Result irrespective of students' gender and school ownership. The study revealed that continuous assessment has influence on student's results and methodologies of learning. Hence, serious attention should be directed towards the tools that are used in conducting the CA. and training of teachers in the setting of CA and examination is very important to students' improved performances.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were suggested by the researcher based on the findings of the study:

- i. Government should sponsor teachers to attend seminars and in-service training in other to update their knowledge and skills on the conduct of continuous assessment.
- ii. More guidance and counselors should be employed into Nigerian secondary schools irrespective of school ownership to help in ensuring that continuous assessment practices of the teachers are properly monitored.
- iii. Teachers in secondary schools, both public and private should endeavor to pay special attention to the practice of continuous assessment based on the principles and concept of the policy in order to reduce the problems of comparability of standards and records.
- iv. Teachers in secondary schools, both public and private should be committed to the use of continuous assessment on a regular basis in order to promptly assess each student's academic and achievement progress as expected for proper and accurate decision making.

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